

yellowing, blast (Bl), and bacterial blight (BB), and resistant to grain discoloration in farmers' fields. Under artificial inoculation, it was moderately resistant to RTV and Bl. In 1984, when

all other medium-duration varieties succumbed to an epidemic outbreak of leaf yellowing, Improved White Ponni tolerated the stress throughout Tamil Nadu. It is moderately resistant to mite

and green leafhopper (GLH), the vector for transmitting RTV (Table 2).

Cooking quality is very good, protein content is 9.88%. ♂

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

No first internode found in Nepalese varieties

G.L. Shrestha, National Rice Improvement Program (NRIP), Parwanipur, Birganj, Nepal

Four groups of Nepalese local cultivars were measured for internode elongation at maturity. Group 1 consisted of 15 local rice varieties that are tall, photoperiod insensitive, and mature within 110 d. Group 2 consisted of seven Gamadi-type local varieties in which the panicle does not exert from heading to maturity but remains enclosed in the flag leaf sheath. Other names for the Gamadi-type are Garvey, Dulhaniya, Kaniya, Thagiya, Sathi, and Satha. These varieties are dwarf type and mature within 100 d. Group 3 consisted of 36 local upland rice cultivars that are tall and mature in 100-110 d. Group 4 consisted of 20 local cultivars that are tall and photoperiod sensitive.

Direct seeding of groups 1, 2, and 3 was on 7 Apr and of group 4 on 15 Jun 1985 in the main plot under normal cultural conditions. Ten main culms were randomly sampled from 10 plants of each variety and culm length, panicle length, and length of each elongated upper internode measured.

All groups except group 2 showed normal elongation of the upper internodes, although total culm length varied significantly (see figure). In group 2, the first internode from the top was absent but the rest of the upper internodes showed normal elongation. This absence of the first internode from the top coincided with panicle enclosure within the flag leaf sheath and is important in the evolution of rice from the wild stage to cultivation. ♂

Elongation (cm)

Internode elongation of Nepalese local germplasm.

Screening for dormancy in 39 rice varieties

H.P. Sikder, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

The 39 varieties screened had these maturity characteristics: 2 early maturing aus, photoperiod insensitive, 90-100 d maturity; 16 early maturing aman, photoperiod sensitive, 140-148 d; 12 medium maturing aman, .

photoperiod sensitive, 160-165 d, and 9 medium-late and late maturing aman, photoperiod sensitive, more than 165 d.

Seeds for three replications were thoroughly dried in the sun, cleaned, and kept in the laboratory in thin cloth bags at room temperature. Germination tests were started 10 d after harvest at regular intervals until dormancy was completely broken.

Seeds were germinated in petri dishes on moist blotting paper for 6 d. When